

Scheme 1

H, 5.88%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 222 (ϵ 13 630), 258 (ϵ 11 150), 303 (ϵ 15 490), 357 (ϵ 178) and 412 nm (ϵ 161).

Similarly, **5b** and **5c** were prepared in 42 and 65% yield, respectively: compound **5b** (Found: C, 44.65; H, 6.97. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2S_2$ calcd. for: C, 45.11; H, 6.70%); $[\eta]_D^{25}$, 1.547; λ_{max} (EtOH) 222 (ϵ 12 750), 250 (ϵ 12 750), 303 (ϵ 16 350), 357 (ϵ 222) and 412 nm (ϵ 176); compound **5c** (Found: C, 49.80; H, 7.63. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2S_2$ calcd. for: C, 49.00; H, 7.40%); $[\eta]_D^{25}$, 1.544; λ_{max} (EtOH) 220 (ϵ , 13 001), 250 (ϵ 12 370), 298 (ϵ 14 920), 357 (ϵ 171) and 412 nm (ϵ 121).

Reaction of unsym. phthaloyl dixanthates (2) with potassium-O-isopropyl-xanthate: Compound **5a**: An acetone solution (40 ml) of *O,O'*-diisopropyl-*S,S'*-phthaloyl-dixanthate (2 g, 0.005 mol) was treated with potassium-*O*-isopropyl-xanthate (0.87 g, 0.005 mol) at room temperature for 30 min. Evaporation of the solvent after removal of unreacted potassium-*O*-isopropyl-xanthate yielded thiophthalic anhydride⁹ (0.4 g, 49%), m.p. 110° (m m.p.) and anhydrosulphide of isopropyl xanthic acid (**5a**; 0.9 g, 76%), m.p. 52–4° (lit. 54°)⁴.

Similarly, **5b** and **5c** were synthesised in 75 and 81% yield, respectively.

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Studies on Biologically Active Heterocycles. Part-II. Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of some New 2-Substituted-amino-5-(2,4- dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles and -thiadiazoles†

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SEVERAL 1,3,4-oxadiazole and -thiadiazole derivatives have been widely reported to exhibit bacteriostatic^{1,2}, hypoglycemic^{3,4}, diuretic⁵, muscle relaxant^{6,7}, analgesic⁸, insecticidal¹, herbicidal^{8,9} and antifungal^{10,11} properties. Keeping this in view, some new 2-substituted-amino-5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**4a–g**) and -thiadiazoles (**5a–h**) were synthesised from the corresponding 1-(2,4-dichlorobenzoyl)-4-arythiosemicarbazides (**3a–h**) by oxidation with iodine in potassium iodide and cyclodehydration with phosphoric acid, respectively, and screened for fungicidal activities against two fungi, *Curvularia verruciformis* and *Alternaria tenuis*. The newly synthesised compounds were characterised on the basis of their elemental analysis and spectroscopic data. The schematic presentation of the reaction sequences are given in Scheme 1.

Experimental

Melting points were determined with a Buchii oil heated apparatus and were uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Parkin—Elmer 237B spectrophotometer using potassium bromide discs. Pmr spectra were determined in solutions stated, with tetramethylsilane as the internal reference and recorded in 60 MHz on a Varian T-60 spectrometer.

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Scheme 1

Mass spectra were recorded on a AEIMS 30 instrument operating at 70 eV.

2,4-Dichlorobenzoic acid ethyl ester (1) was prepared by the usual esterification method. 2,4-Dichlorobenzoylhydrazine (2) was prepared following the literature^{1,2} method. 1-(2,4-Dichlorobenzoyl)-4-arylthiosemicarbazides were prepared according to the method of Goswami *et al.*^{1,3}.

2-Substituted-amino-5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4a) :

Method A : 1-(2,4-Dichlorobenzoyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (3 ; 3.9 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved/suspended in ethanol (95%, 30 ml), and 4N sodium hydroxide (5 ml) was added with cooling and shaking. To the clear solution, iodine in 5% potassium iodide solution was added gradually with stirring till the colour of iodine persisted at room temperature. The contents were then heated under reflux on a water-bath and more iodine solution was added carefully till permanent tinge of excess iodine remained. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water (500 ml), the precipitated solid filtered off, washed with water and warm carbon disulphide, and crystallised from dilute ethanol (charcoal). The compounds (4b-g) were prepared by this method using differently substituted arylthiosemicarbazide (Table 1).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4 AND 5

Compd. no.	R	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
					C	N
4a	C ₆ H ₅	77	194	C ₁₄ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl ₂	54.52 (54.90)	13.60 (13.72)
4b	<i>p</i> -OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	66	185	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl ₂	56.40 (56.25)	13.20 (13.12)
4c	<i>o</i> -OOH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	72	153	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	53.62 (53.57)	12.42 (12.60)
4d	<i>p</i> OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	81	178	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	53.52 (53.57)	12.42 (12.50)
4e	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	80	181	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Cl ₂	56.51 (56.25)	13.41 (13.12)
4f	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	75	221	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	47.53 (47.86)	15.83 (15.95)
4g	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	70	187	C ₁₄ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl ₃	49.44 (49.33)	12.52 (12.33)
5a	C ₆ H ₅	72	238	C ₁₄ H ₉ SN ₂ Cl ₂	52.52 (52.17)	12.51 (13.02)
5b	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	82	238	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ SN ₂ Cl ₂	45.81 (45.77)	15.42 (15.25)
5c	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	73	238	C ₁₄ H ₉ SN ₂ Cl ₃	47.22 (47.12)	11.52 (11.78)
5d	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	82	164	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ OSN ₂ Cl ₂	51.20 (51.13)	11.81 (11.93)
5e	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	76	167	C ₁₄ H ₉ SN ₂ Cl ₃	47.29 (47.12)	11.62 (11.78)
5f	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	82	198	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ SN ₂ Cl ₂	53.91 (53.57)	12.80 (12.50)
5g	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	80	300	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ SN ₂ Cl ₂	45.52 (45.77)	15.81 (15.25)
5h	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₅	63	175	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ SN ₂ Cl ₂	53.32 (53.57)	12.61 (12.50)

* Compounds 4a-g prepared by method-A were analysed for C and N.

Method B¹⁵: The thiosemicarbazide (3; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in methanol and mercuric oxide (0.011 mol) was added to it. The contents were refluxed for 2–4 h and then filtered hot. The filtrate thus obtained was evaporated and the resulting solid recrystallised from dilute alcohol; other compounds of the series were prepared similarly (Table 1) (Found: C, 54.52; N, 13.60. C₁₄H₉N₃OCl calcd. for: C, 54.90 N, 13.72%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 150–3 390 (NH), 1 610 (C=N) and 1 250–1 270 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C); δ (TMS; DMSO-d₆) 6.50–8.00 (9H, m, Ar–H and NH).

2-Substituted-amino-5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole¹⁶ (5a): The thiosemicarbazide (3a; 3.40 g, 0.01 mol) was added gradually with stirring during 20 min to syrupy phosphoric acid (85%, 25 ml) at 120°. The mixture was heated under stirring at that temperature for further 30 min and then poured into ice-water (500 ml) and left overnight. The precipitated solid was filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (95%, charcoal) to afford 5a; all the thiadiazole derivatives thus prepared are listed in Table 1 (Found: C, 52.32; N, 12.50. C₁₄H₉N₃SCl₂ calcd. for: C, 52.17; N, 13.04%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 175–3 320 (NH) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (TMS; DMSO-d₆) 6.6–8.2 (9H, m, Ar–H and NH).

Fungitoxic activity: The synthesised compounds were screened for their fungitoxic properties using the method of Horsfall and Rich¹⁷ on two test organisms, *Curvularia verruciformis* and *Alternaria tenuis*. The percentage of conidial inhibition was calculated by comparing the percentage germination of treated slides with the control. Average results of four replications are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PERCENTAGE INHIBITION OF CONIDIAL GERMINATION IN TEST SOLUTIONS

Compd. no.	% Inhibition*	
	<i>C. verruciformis</i>	<i>A. tenuis</i>
4a	+	—
4b	—	—
4c	—	—
4d	—	—
4e	—	—
4f	—	—
4g	—	—
5a	+	+
5b	+	—
5c	++++	+++
5d	+	—
5e	+	+
5f	—	—
5g	—	—
5h	+	+

* (—) = No inhibition, (+) = 0–25%, (++) = 25–50%, (+++) = 51–75%, and (++++) = 76–100% inhibition.

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Partial Amino Terminal Sequence of Globulin from *Phaseolus vulgaris*, *Vigna mungo* and *Vigna radiata*

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A variety of beans is cultivated throughout India and constitute a major dietary protein source for vegetarian population. Several workers^{1–4} have reported the isolation of major storage protein from *Phaseolus vulgaris* consisting of glycoproteins and globulins of high molecular weight containing bound carbohydrate. Recently, we isolated⁵ pure homogeneous major protein globulin from three edible beans, viz. *P. vulgaris* Linn. (french beans), *Vigna mungo* Linn. (black gram) and *V. radiata* Linn. (green gram) using gel filtration and electrophoresis followed by determination of amino acid composition of each protein using standard methods of chromatography⁶ and spectrophotometry^{7,8}. Present communication reports the NH₂-terminal Edman degradation and partial sequence of each protein.